

Relativistic Doppler effect

Harald Schröer

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We view at the following figure:

The reference system S' is moving with the constant velocity v compared with the reference system S . The motion shall be parallel to the x -axis. The wave-exciting device W is in the reference system S' , the observer B in the reference system S . We introduce the following quantities:

f, f' = emitting frequency, shifted frequency
 λ, λ' = emitting wavelength, shifted wavelength
 t, t' = times in the reference systems S and S'
 c = light velocity

We use the wave equation in the form:

$$y = \sin 2\pi \left(f \cdot t - \frac{x}{\lambda} \right)$$

The amplitude of the wave shall be 1.

Now we need the Lorentz-transformations:

$$x = \frac{x' + vt'}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

$$t = \frac{t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

We insert these equations in the wave equation:

$$y = \sin 2\pi \left(f \cdot \frac{t' + \frac{vx'}{c^2}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} - \frac{1}{\lambda} \cdot \frac{x' + vt'}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \right)$$

Wir sort:

$$y = \sin \left(\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \cdot \left(ft' - \frac{vt'}{\lambda} + \frac{vfx'}{c^2} - \frac{x'}{\lambda} \right) \right)$$

Both terms with t' represent the receiver frequency. With the relation $c = f \cdot \lambda$ we get:

$$f' = \frac{f - \frac{v}{\lambda}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} = \frac{f \cdot \lambda - v}{\lambda \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} = \frac{c - v}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \cdot \frac{f}{c}$$

For the receiver frequency we obtain:

$$f' = f \cdot \frac{1 - \frac{v}{c}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} = f \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1 - \frac{v}{c}}{1 + \frac{v}{c}}}$$

We get the receiver wavelength with $\lambda' = \frac{c}{f'}$:

$$\lambda' = \frac{c}{f} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c}}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}}$$

For the wavelength displacement we have:

$$\Delta\lambda = \lambda \cdot \left(\sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c}}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}} - 1 \right)$$

or:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c}}{1 - \frac{v}{c}}} - 1 = \frac{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}{1 - \frac{v}{c}} - 1$$

This is the equation for the relativistic Doppler effect in the astronomy.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "Particular problems of special relativity theory" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002